

Test Instructions

Welcome, and thank you for participating!

Please follow the instructions below carefully to ensure a smooth testing process.

Enrollment

- Enroll in one of the 10 groups in the Opal course.
- Try to distribute yourselves evenly among the groups.

Accessing the Test

- Once enrolled, you will receive an access link to one of the test versions.
- The test versions only differ in the order of questions; the tasks themselves remain the same.
- All data collected will be used solely for research purposes, and all answers will remain anonymous.

Test Duration

- The total time for the test is **30 minutes**, plus an additional **2 minutes** to finalize and submit everything.

Materials Allowed

- You may use a **pen and blank paper** as aids during the test.

Important Guidelines

- **Justifications are required** for your answers—answers without justifications will not be counted.
- Ensure that you **complete the entire test** before submission.

Access to Answers

- If you would like to receive the answers to the tasks, please send an email request to luisa.bartl@s2018.tu-chemnitz.de

Thank you, and good luck!

Example:

Task 1

This is an example?

Please justify in 1-3 sentences why your answer is correct and why the others are not. You will only get a point for the answer and the justification.

Select all that apply

Option 1

Option 2

Option 3

Justification:

*

Please respond to the following statements according to your experience. There are no right or wrong answers - the important thing is to answer honestly and spontaneously.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1. The task was clear and unambiguous.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. The difficulty level of the task matched my skill and experience.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. I felt I had sufficient time to complete the task without feeling rushed.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*

Did you experience any technical difficulties while completing the task?

Choose one of the following answers

Yes, I did.

No, I did not.

Background

- There is no official definition of code comprehension.
- The goal of this test is to create a universal assessment that measures different aspects of code comprehension, to work towards finding a definition.
- The insights gained can help improve both learning and teaching practices related to code comprehension.